

ANGOLA'S ACCESSION TO THE SADC FREE TRADE AREA

SADC Director of Industrial Development and Trade

Interviewer:

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How do you characterize the evolution of Angola's negotiating position, concerning the SADC FTA, emphasizing the need to its industrialization?

Interviewee:

Following the release of Angola's roadmap for implementation of the FTA during the meeting of SADC Ministers of Trade held in July 2018, the process is still in its early stages of internal consultations. This consultative process will see the development of a draft national strategy for trade integration based on sectoral inputs and on the findings and conclusions of the impact studies conducted and discussions held with the stakeholders. This will then culminate in the development of Angola's FTA tariff offer, which will also be subject to a validation exercise involving internal stakeholders before being presented to SADC Member States by June 2019 for negotiation.

Interviewer:

What role has the SADC Executive Secretariat played in the negotiation of Angola's adhesion to the SADC FTA?

Interviewee:

As indicated above the negotiations are still to commence. The Secretariat will assist whenever required, i.e. in the process to prepare Angola's tariff offer and it will facilitate the negotiations between Angola and other SADC Members to finalise the offer for implementation.

Interviewer:

Do you think that the social and historical interaction of states and negotiators has influenced the position of Angola and other states? How do you describe them?

Angola is a founding member of SADC and potentially a major player in regional trade and this naturally will have a bearing on the positions and trajectory of the negotiations once they are underway during the middle of next year. We will of course have a greater appreciation of the question once that process evolves and finalizes.

Interviewer:

Can SADC organizational structures be considered as an element of regional socialization of States?

Interviewee:

Regional socialization if defined in terms of the extent members in an organization internalize that organisation's norms and practices in the way they conduct their affairs, is in the case of SADC indeed articulated through its structures, treaties and protocols. It is a measure of success how an organisation's tenets and principles define its members' economic, trade, political and other activities. What can be assessed is how far SADC has succeeded in this regard. However throughout its existence it will always promote and endeavor for greater regional cohesion and adherence to achievement of common goals for its members.

Interviewer:

Have you had a direct intervention into this negotiation? How do you describe it?

Interviewee:

The status of Angola's FTA process as of now is provided elsewhere above. Whilst the negotiations proper are still to commence, the tabling of a clear FTA roadmap by Angola was a commendable major step and acknowledged as such by SADC Trade Ministers at their July 2018 meeting. It was a culmination of a process that saw the matter consistently tabled and discussed at various SADC technical and Ministerial meetings over the years. The Secretariat's role has been one of facilitating those discussions and making sure that the matter does not fade away from the SADC agenda. That facilitative role will continue during the tariff offer negotiations and on implementation when Angola becomes a full party to the SADC FTA.